

PHOTO BIOLOGY : AN APPLICATION TO PHOTO CHEMISTRY

By

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For Full Text is composed of three important comments . 1. STERN VOLMER EQUATION AND LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS : Abstracting of an article as Indian Science Abstract . (ISSN : 0019-6339 , Vol 43). 2. ANALYSIS OF FLUORESCENCE QUENCHING RATE CONSTANT : In this note we wish to report the Photo Dynamic Application of STERN VOLMER EQUATION relating to Quenching rate constant to predict photo-dynamic therapy (PDT). 3. Modeled Photo Sensitized Complex : Published in the The J. of Institution of Chemists (India) , V.80 (5), 2008 .p.148.

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1. Jaydip Datta , A PHOTODYNAMIC CHEMO THERAPY : A REVIEW , August 2019,

DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.19647.87202/6](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19647.87202/6) .

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2. Jaydip Datta , A Photo Sensitized CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC modeled complex , September 2019 , DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/3](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/3) .

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